

TEACHING PROFESSION IN A DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY

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Abstract. *This article describes the essence of the teaching profession in a democratic society, the right to engage in pedagogical activities, the status of pedagogical staff and the guarantees of their activities, the obligations of pedagogical staff*

Keywords: *pedagogic profession, pedagogical activity, status of pedagogic staff, responsibilities of pedagogic staff*

Taking into account today's requirements, the personal qualities and professional qualities of a teacher can be defined as follows:

as personal qualities: highly spiritual, cultured, enlightened, humane and tolerant, able to promote and solve perspective tasks for the development of the continuous education system, independently set the goal in social and political life able to contribute to the development of society.

Professional qualities include creative and social activity, ideological and moral maturity, high professional culture through scientific-theoretical, pedagogical-psychological, scientific-methodical training.

The right to engage in pedagogical activities. Chapter 5, Article 44 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" provides the legal status of pedagogic employees of educational organizations. Persons with appropriate education, professional training and moral and ethical qualities have the right to engage in pedagogical activities. Individuals who have completed a master's degree and specialists with a diploma have the right to engage in pedagogical activities in their specialty. If the legislation does not provide otherwise, persons without a higher pedagogical education are given the right to engage in pedagogical activities in educational organizations (except for higher education organizations) after passing retraining courses. Masters of industrial education have the right to engage in pedagogical activities in professional educational organizations without passing retraining courses. If necessary, professional educational organizations employ masters of production education, as well as other specialists without higher education who have relevant knowledge and practical skills to conduct practical and additional training. can attract.

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Article 45 of Chapter 5 of the Law on the Status of Pedagogical Employees and Guarantees of Their Activities provides the status of pedagogical employees and guarantees of their activities. The status of teaching staff is recognized by society and the state. Pedagogical employees are provided with social support, organizational and legal conditions are created for the implementation of their professional activities, to increase their social status and reputation, as well as guarantees for the realization of their rights and legal interests. The rights, honor, dignity, and work reputation of the teaching staff of educational organizations are under the protection of the state. Educational organizations are not allowed to interfere in the professional activities of pedagogues, to influence the correct and impartial assessment of the knowledge of learners, as well as to prevent these pedagogues from fulfilling their service obligations. Pedagogical employees have the following rights: to protect their honor, dignity and professional reputation; development and implementation of author's programs within the framework of educational programs, development of teaching methodology, as well as use of relevant educational subjects, courses, modules, and creative activity; free choice and use of modern pedagogical forms, teaching and training tools, methods; demand that necessary conditions be created for them to carry out their professional activities; free use of the services of educational, scientific and methodological information-resource centers; participation in the development of state educational standards, state educational requirements, qualification requirements, curricula and educational programs; implementation of scientific, research and creative activities, participation in experimental activities, development and implementation of innovations; participation in the management of the educational organization, as well as in the discussion of issues related to the activity of the educational organization; to be a member of trade unions and non-governmental non-commercial organizations, to be representatives of their employees, to participate in the activities of other institutions of civil society; join public associations of pedagogues to express and protect their professional rights and common interests; protection from interference in one's professional activity; free medical examination in state health institutions (for state educational institutions and organizations); participation in the protection of the rights and legal interests of learners. Pedagogical employees may have other rights in accordance with the law. It is forbidden to engage teaching staff in any other work that is not related to their job duties.

Chapter 5, Article 46 of the Law on Obligations of Pedagogical Employees deals with the obligations of pedagogical employees. Pedagogical staff: respect the honor, dignity and professional reputation of the participants of the educational process; conducting quality training sessions; use of information and communication technologies, advanced and innovative forms and methods of teaching and upbringing; to take into account the psychological and unique characteristics, physical and mental health, and physiological development of learners, to pay attention to the creation of conditions for the education of persons with physical, mental, sensory (sense) or mental disabilities; to conduct educational work with minors in cooperation with their parents or other legal representatives; compliance with the charter and (or) other founding documents of the educational organization, rules of the internal labor procedure; to regularly improve his qualifications, to undergo periodic attestation in terms of suitability for the position

he holds; must undergo a medical examination on time. Pedagogical staff may have other obligations in accordance with the law, as well as the contract concluded between the learner and the educational organization. Pedagogical employees are prohibited from committing actions contrary to moral and ethical norms in the implementation of pedagogical activities. Requirements for the clothing of teaching staff are determined by educational organizations.

General requirements for professors and teachers of undergraduate education and master's specialties:

Qualified teachers (specialists with a master's degree or diploma), candidates of sciences, philosophy doctor (PhD), associate professors, doctor of science (DSc), professors, persons with scientific, pedagogical and creative titles, as well as highly qualified specialists and practitioners with experience should be involved.

Candidates of science, doctor of philosophy (PhD), associate professors, doctor of science (DSc) and professors, who have scientific, pedagogical and creative titles (degrees) in the subject taught in the implementation of the master's curriculum and curriculum highly qualified specialists and practitioners should be involved.

The teacher is a pedagogue, an employee of the continuous education system, and is engaged in teaching pupils and students. Other names: "*teacher*". A teacher - a specialist who carries out educational work with students in secondary general education schools of various directions, academic lyceums, vocational schools, colleges and technical schools. High school teachers are called "domla", they are also referred to by a general name like "professor-teacher". The term "teacher" or "pedagogue" is also used for teachers.

It should be said that a teacher is a special social phenomenon, and his personal qualities are more important than professional qualities because he influences the formation of society members. Because it shapes the image of society today and tomorrow. That is why it is not enough for a teacher to be professionally mature. His spiritual world should be saturated with good human qualities that are expected to be instilled in students. Special attention is paid to this aspect in educational institutions where teachers are trained.

The modern science of pedagogy notes that the teacher has practical, research, organizing, mediating, executive tasks. Only a teacher who fully fulfills these tasks can influence the formation of today's young generation as well-rounded individuals. Finding such characteristics in the teachers of the period of independence is a factor of ensuring the development of the country.

Today, a teacher should acquire modern methodical knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies. Innovative educational environment requires teachers to acquire and apply the following knowledge:

- practical activities related to the use of innovative technologies in teaching;
- practical activity in strengthening the material and technical base of teaching;
- activities in the implementation of professional orientation in teaching.

The practical activities of the teacher in connection with the application of innovative technologies in the educational process are the following stages:

- determining the ways of using innovative technologies in pedagogical practice while mastering the methodological bases;
- designing the educational process based on the requirements of innovative technologies;
- selection and introduction of innovative technologies, taking into account the didactic goals of all classroom and extracurricular forms of teaching, independent education;

- to analyze and summarize the results obtained from this process, to identify gaps in students' knowledge, skills and qualifications, and to determine ways to eliminate them.

Professional knowledge is information necessary for work. Skill is the readiness and ability to perform the action, use the necessary techniques, and act in the work environment to solve this task. A skill is a permanent skill, an activity that is automated through constant repetition. Professional knowledge is theoretical scientific information and knowledge, as well as awareness in a specific field of activity, necessary for the quality performance of service tasks in order to achieve results in professional activity.

"21st Century Competencies" include the skills and abilities needed by educators, business leaders, academics and government agencies to succeed in 21st century society and workplaces. It is part of a growing international movement focusing on the skills students need to prepare for success in a rapidly changing digital society. Many of these skills are also linked to deeper learning based on the acquisition of skills such as analytical thinking, complex problem solving and teamwork. These skills differ from traditional academic skills because they are not primarily based on content knowledge.

Preparing individuals for a profession involves providing them with a complex set of skills. These skills prepare them for the future and help them cope with unpredictable situations. Here's a list of 12 21st-century career skills that will help you prepare for your next job:

Creativity. Many jobs today require creativity. Any organization or industry that wants to grow is usually looking for creative professionals. Organizations can adapt to changing markets and overcome challenges by trying different things. Creative thinking can be used to generate new ideas, change perspectives, and develop unique solutions to problems. And this helps to develop in an ever-evolving world. For example, an outdated curriculum can be identified and new technology can be used or developed to meet the requirements.

Critical thinking. Critical thinking helps identify and evaluate a situation using relevant evidence. Using the ability of critical thinking, it is possible to filter and organize information, evidence, concepts to identify and solve any problem. Skilled professionals are usually able to think critically for practical solutions and sound judgments. Critical thinking skills allow to objectively assess the situation, identify options and predict possible consequences. Organizations generally value professionals who are proactive enough to see and plan for future problems before they occur.

Collaboration. Collaboration is another important skill that can help a person excel in their career, regardless of their role. Collaboration involves being a good listener, communicating and collaborating ("partnering") with others to achieve a specific goal. Organizations can hire people who have experience and high knowledge in their field. Being able to work with others means you can benefit from their experience. Collaboration skills teach an individual to be versatile and provide important benefits and adjustments to improve the overall performance and productivity of their team.

Communication. Development of useful communication skills helps in clearly presenting goals, tasks and requirements in the socialization of a person. This may indicate that the person is receiving very reliable information and working smoothly in the team. Knowing and being proficient in using the correct etiquette for different communication situations can often be very helpful.

Information and media literacy. Information literacy is essential when conducting market research, preparing a report, or evaluating a presentation. Acknowledging reliable and factual information is essential to making sound and informed decisions in personal and professional life. Mastering information literacy involves knowing how to find information, analyze its accuracy, and adapt it to different scenarios. Media literacy skills help you identify reliable sources for news, empirical research, and other information on a variety of platforms.

Technological literacy. Having a solid foundation of computer skills is essential in the 21st century. Today, the workplace is full of technology, from online calendars to accounting software and project management tools. Having basic digital literacy skills can make it easier to understand new types of technology for work or personal use. For example, digital literacy can help you organize a video call, share ideas with colleagues, and collaborate and communicate effectively.

Social skills. Learning social skills can make it easier to work with others because they show how to be professional and considerate at work. If a person has strong social and interpersonal skills, they can usually communicate more successfully and build strong partnerships with colleagues and prospective clients. Applying these skills can help improve other important skills such as teamwork or leadership. Manners, attitudes, courtesy and empathy play an important role in society and can influence business decisions.

Leadership. Leadership skills can include taking initiative, solving problems, conflicts, and learning to take responsibility for one's own and team members' actions. Proactive, proactive and strong leaders can help their colleagues improve the quality of work and productivity, which is why most employers value strong leadership skills. When working on group projects or starting a new role for the first time, leadership can help develop skills, prepare for future leadership positions, and advance your career.

Adaptability. In the labor market, dynamic and versatile professionals are valuable to employers for many reasons. Such individuals can work well online or offline, independently and as a team. They can take and give instructions and respond equally to feedback. If an individual can adapt to changing work environments and industry structures, he or she can be a desirable job candidate and overall strong professional. Flexibility refers to a person's willingness to learn new things, take on additional responsibilities, and adapt to organizational changes.

Global awareness. In the era of globalization, many businesses operate worldwide, providing opportunities to connect with people around the world or work abroad. Learning about different countries and communities, cultural norms and their ways of life helps to better appreciate the members of the international community and adapt to changes. Recognizing and respecting these differences will help you collaborate more effectively, expand your professional network, and find new career prospects.

Decision making. It is important that every professional can make the right decision for his organization. Effective decision-making skills help you approach problems and offer constructive solutions with minimal risk. Decision-making is an important skill that involves deciding between different strategies to solve a problem.

Problem solve. Hiring managers often use the term "problem solving" to describe the ability to skillfully manage difficult or unpredictable situations at work. Individuals who can assess various problems and offer quick solutions are generally in high demand. This skill is also useful in other aspects of your professional life, such as networking and making day-to-day decisions. Effective problem solving may also involve technical expertise and expertise relevant to specific

fields or roles. Possessing problem-solving skills typically means having strong analytical, creative, and critical thinking skills. In many countries around the world, future teachers will be required to learn 21st century skills as part of their curriculum.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the teacher's professional knowledge is about the essence of the teacher's work in pedagogical and psychological terms, pedagogical activity and communication characteristics, the teacher's personality, the mental development of students, their age characteristics, etc. is information. The teacher creates standards from professional knowledge for his personal professional development. Pedagogical skill - teacher's pedagogical actions (effects). Like other skills, pedagogical skills are activities that are performed at a sufficiently high level. Pedagogical skill forms "technique" in teacher's activity.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2018-yil 10-oktabrdagi 816-son qaroriga 4-ilova «Oliy va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limi tizimi uchun o'quv adabiyotlarini yaratishga qo'yilgan talablar».
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining «Ta'lim to'g'risida»gi Qonuni, 23.09.2020 yildagi 637-son
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2020-yil 31-dekabrda 824-son qaroriga 1-ilovasi «Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'quv jarayoniga kredit-modul tizimini joriy etish tartibi to'g'risida» nizom
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirining 2021 yil 19 oktabrdagi 11-son buyrug'iga ilova. O'zbekiston Respublikasining DAVLAT STANDARTI. Oliy ta'limning davlat ta'lim standarti Oliy ta'lim yo'nalishlari va mutaxassisliklari klassifikatori.
5. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
6. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
7. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
8. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
9. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – T. 48. – №. 12.
10. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
11. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
12. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
13. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
14. <https://stat.edu.uz/Univer-list.php>

15. <https://xs.uz/uz/post/amir-temur-va-temurijlar-davri-renessansida-talim-tizimining-tutgan-ahamiyati>
16. <https://www.blendedlearning.org/models/>